
QuikSCAT/SeaWinds Twice-Daily SIR-Enhanced Scatterometer *EASE-Grid 2.0* Radar Backscatter

Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document

Version 1.0

December 31, 2024

David G. Long¹ and Julie Z. Miller²

¹ *Microwave Earth Remote Sensing Laboratory, Brigham Young University, Provo, UT, USA*

² *Earth Science and Observation Center, Cooperative Institute for Research in Environmental Sciences, University of Colorado, Boulder, CO, USA*

Cover Image

Color montage of morning overpass AMSR2 horizontally-polarized 36 GHz passive microwave brightness temperatures, 29–30 June, 2003, by M. J. Brodzik, National Snow and Ice Data Center.

Citation

David G. Long and Julie Z. Miller. 2024. QuikSCAT/SeaWinds Twice-Daily SIR-Enhanced Scatterometer EASE-Grid 2.0 Radar Backscatter Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document, Version 1.0. NSIDC White Paper. <https://doi.org/TBD>.

Contents

1	Revision History	9
2	Acronyms and Abbreviations	10
3	Purpose of this Document	12
4	Gridded and SIR-Enhanced Product Description	14
4.1	Product Description	14
4.2	SeaWinds Instrument Background	14
5	QuikSCAT and SeaWinds Sampling	18
5.1	Time Division	19
5.1.1	Day Boundary Effects	20
5.1.2	Polar Swath Overlap	22
5.2	Orbital Drift	27
6	Morning and Evening LTOD Division	30
6.1	Temporal Resolution Example	30
6.2	LTOD Over Multiple Days	32
6.3	Grid Spatial Extent	33
6.4	Grid Spatial Resolution	35
6.5	Data Products	36
7	Algorithm Description	38
7.1	Background	38
7.2	QSCAT Backscatter Image Products	38
7.3	Radar Spatial Response and Image Reconstruction	39
7.3.1	Local-Time-of-Day	44
7.4	Incidence Angle Effects	45
7.5	Azimuth Angle Effects	45
7.6	Data Volume	48
8	Acknowledgements	49
9	References	50
	Appendices	53
A	QSCAT Projections and Grids	53

B	QSCAT Data Definition	54
B.1	File Requirements	54
B.2	Filename Convention	54
B.3	File Content, v1.0	55

List of Figures

1	SeaWinds observation swath	12
2	Illustration of (top row) egg and (bottom row) slice SRFs and how they vary as a function of antenna rotation angle for (left column) H-pol [the inner-beam] and (right column) V-pol [the outer-beam] measurements. Contours are shown at -3 dB from the peak response. For clarity, only contours are shown for slices that often overlap. For the purposes of visualization, the plots have been horizontally shifted to appear close together whereas they are actually very far apart. The jagged edges of the slice contours are the result of the quantized grid on which the SRF is evaluated.	16
3	More detailed illustration of the MRSF of a particular (left column) egg and (right column) slice measurements for (top row) H-pol and (bottom row) V-pol. The slices shown are from different measurements that happened to cover the same small box area (the small filled box). Contours are shown at -3, -6, -9 and -12 dB from the peak response. The image area is 100 km × 100 km. The large square box is 22.25 km. The small box is 2.225 km. For clarity, slices are offset from the center as indicated by the positions of the small squares.	17
4	A fall QuikSCAT Arctic σ^o (in dB) images. (left) Typical one-day v-pol image made with all passes in one day. (center) Same image masked to show the coverage of a single pass. (right) Same image masked to show the coverage of two consecutive passes. (Note: these images show only part of the standard EASE-2.0 Grid Northern Hemisphere projection area used for the standard QSCAT product.)	18
5	QuikSCAT swath coverage near the North pole illustrating the transition from morning pass to evening pass. The pole is in the center. The lines radiating out from the center depict hourly boundaries. (left) Dark blue indicates measurements flagged as Ascending in the L1B data, while yellow denotes measurements flagged as Descending. The beige area contains both ascending- and descending-flagged measurements. (right) Idealized ascending/descending flagging of individual measurements, which in this case corresponds to LTOD division.	20
6	Average UTC time of day in mins for (left) ascending and (right) descending passes for day of year (DOY) 258, 2003. Note the areas of confused time of day to swath overlap that are widely spaced in time.	21
7	Image showing the difference in time of day of the ascending and descending passes in Fig. 6. Time separation in minutes – descending first is positive. . .	22

8 Maps of raw LTOD over the Southern Hemisphere within a particular single UTC day (10 Jan 2000) extending northward to 60°S in a polar stereographic projection with the pole at the center. Each left/right panel pair shows morning and evening LTODs. Yellow indicates that the raw LTOD is within the UTC day. Green indicates that the raw LTOD is prior to the UTC day. Brown indicates that raw LTOD is after the end of the UTC day. Compare with Fig. 9. (upper left) First pass of day. Note that the data (at 00:00 UTC) begins near the pole and extends to the right, moving from evening LTOD to morning LTOD. (upper right) Second pass of day. (center left) Third pass of day. (center right) Fourth pass of day. (lower left) Fifth pass of day. (lower right) Last pass of day, which ends just before the pole. 23

9 Maps of raw LTOD over the Northern Hemisphere within a particular single UTC day (10 Jan 2000) extending southward to 60°N in a polar stereographic projection with the pole at the center. Compare with Fig. 8. (upper left) First pass of day. (evening precedes morning) (upper right) Second pass of day. (center left) Third pass of day. (center right) Fourth pass of day. (lower left) Fifth pass of day. (lower right) Last pass of day. 24

10 Coverage images that show how nine consecutive passes of QuikSCAT overlap in the Arctic for (left) full passes (ascending and descending), (center) only the swath portions flagged as ascending, and (right) only the swath portions flagged as descending passes. Pixel color shows the number of swath passes over that pixel. 25

11 Histograms of the LTOD of QuikSCAT egg σ^o measurements within a 1° latitude band centered at (left) 30°S, (center) 60°S, and (right) 70°S for a 24 hr period. (Northern hemisphere distributions are similar). Dashed red lines show division lines at 00:00 and 12:00 h. 26

12 Two-dimensional histograms of the LTOD of QuikSCAT egg σ^o measurements within a 1° latitude band centered at (left) 30°S, (center) 60°S, and (right) 70°S versus longitude for a 24 hr period. (Northern hemisphere distributions are similar). Dashed red lines show division lines at 00:00 and 12:00 h. . . . 26

13 Histograms of the LTOD of SeaWinds egg σ^o measurements within a 1° latitude band centered at (left) 30°S, (center) 60°S, and (right) 70°S for a 24 hr period. (Northern hemisphere distributions are similar). Dashed red lines show QuikSCAT division lines at 00:00 and 12:00 hrs. Dashed green lines show SeaWinds division lines at 04:00 and 16:00 hrs. Compare Fig. 11. . . . 27

14 Two-dimensional histograms of the LTOD of SeaWinds egg σ^o measurements within a 1° latitude band centered at (left) 30°S, (center) 60°S, and (right) 70°S versus longitude for a 24 hr period. (Northern hemisphere distributions are similar). Dashed red lines show QuikSCAT division lines at 00:00 and 12:00 hrs. Dashed green lines show SeaWinds division lines at 04:00 and 16:00 hrs. Compare Fig. 12. 28

15 Histograms of the LTOD of (left column) QuikSCAT, (center column) SeaWinds, and (right column) tandem mission (combined QuikSCAT and SeaWinds) egg σ^o measurements within a 1° latitude band centered at (top row) 70°S and (bottom row) 70°N for a 24 hr period. Dashed red lines show QuikSCAT division lines at 00:00 and 12:00 hrs. Dashed green lines show SeaWinds division lines at 04:00 and 16:00 hrs. 28

16 Difference in the longitude of the ascending node of orbits exactly 4 days apart during most of QuikSCAT’s nominal wind mission. Spikes are the result of orbits when QuikSCAT was not operating. 29

17 Timeseries plot comparing the ascending/descending method (top) of data segregation and the new morning/evening method (bottom) (84.0468 N 135.3773 W from DOY 163 to DOY 166, 2003). Note the morning/evening method follows transients better and is closer to uniform samples. 31

18 Count of number of passes from seven consecutive passes overlap in (left) morning and (right) evening data in the Arctic. Pixel color shows the number of swaths that passed over each pixel. Compare with Fig. 10. 32

19 Maps of raw LTOD over the equatorial region within a particular single UTC day (10 Jan 2000). (left) Shows morning while (right) shows evening raw LTOD labeling. Yellow indicates that the raw LTOD is within the UTC day. Green indicates that the raw LTOD is prior to the UTC day. Brown indicates that raw LTOD is after the end of the UTC day. The prime meridian in the center with latitude extending $\pm 67^\circ$. Compare to Figs. 8 and 9. 33

20 Northern and Southern EASE-Grid 2.0 projection extents 34

21 Cylindrical EASE-Grid 2.0 projection extents 34

22 EASE2-M vs. EASE2-T extents 35

23 25 km nested resolutions 36

24 GRD vs. SIR component measurement concept 39

25 Comparison of the effective PSRF of pixels for egg and slice image formation. For this illustrative example coarse grid is 22.5 km while the fine grid is 2.225 km. This example is for H-pol, but V-pol is similar. The size of each panel is 100 km \times 100 km. Linear gray scale. Contours are shown at -3, -6, -9, and -12 dB from the peak response. (Long, 2017a) 42

26 Extracted QuikSCAT H-pol images created from four days (254-257, 1999) of data for different cases of algorithm. Scale in dB. Note the finer detail apparent in the SIR-enhanced images. (Long, 2017a) 43

27 Scatter density of QuikSCAT σ^o in dB versus azimuth angle for two polar study regions. A second-order FA model fit to the data is shown as the light grey line. Data is from a single 4-day orbit repeat cycle on days DOY 10-13, 2005. 47

List of Tables

1	ATBD Revision History	9
2	Data Set Revision History	9
3	List of Acronyms and Abbreviations	10
4	QSCAT Grids	36
5	Available twice-daily QuikSCAT image products. (1999-2009)	37
6	Available thrice-daily tandem (QuikSCAT and SeaWinds) image products. (2003 only)	37
7	25 km Projections and Grid Dimensions	53
8	Filenaming Convention	55

1 Revision History

Table 1: *ATBD Revision History*

Revision	Date	Purpose
1.0	2024-03-01	Initial Version

Table 2: *Data Set Revision History*

Revision	Date	Purpose
1.0	2024-03-01	Initial Data Release

2 Acronyms and Abbreviations

Table 3: List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

ADEOS	Advanced Earth Observing Satellite
ATBD	Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document
AVE	weighted AVeraging image formation algorithm
bSIR	Scatterometer Image Reconstruction using binary response function
BYU	Brigham Young University
CDR	Climate Data Record
CETB	Calibrated Passive Microwave Daily EASE-Grid 2.0 Brightness Temperature
CF	Climate and Forecast Metadata Conventions
DAAC	Distributed Active Archive Center
dB	decibel ($10 \log_{10}$)
DIB	Drop-In-the-Bucket averaging (used to produce GRD products)
DOY	Day Of Year
E2N	EASE-Grid 2.0, Northern Hemisphere Projection
E2S	EASE-Grid 2.0, Southern Hemisphere Projection
E2T	EASE-Grid 2.0, Temperate and Tropical Cylindrical Projection
EASE-Grid	Equal-Area Scalable Earth Grid (Original Definition)
EASE-Grid 2.0	Equal-Area Scalable Earth Grid Version 2.0
EASE2-M	EASE-Grid 2.0, Mid- and Low-Latitude Cylindrical Projection
EASE2-N	EASE-Grid 2.0, Northern Hemisphere Projection
EASE2-S	EASE-Grid 2.0, Southern Hemisphere Projection
EASE2-T	EASE-Grid 2.0, Temperate and Tropical Cylindrical Projection
EIA	Earth Incidence Angle
EOSDIS	Earth Observing System Data and Information System
ESDR	Earth System Data Record
FA	incidence-angle Fixed Azimuth modulation coefficients
FCDR	Fundamental Climate Data Record
GHz	GigaHertz
GRD	(Drop-In-the-Bucket) Gridding Method
HH	Horizontal-polarization transmit, Horizontal-polarization receive
JPL	Jet Propulsion Laboratory
LTOD	local-time-of-day
MEaSURES	Making Earth System Data Records for Use in Research Environments
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NSCAT	NASA Scatterometer
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration

Acronyms and Abbreviations

NORAD	North American Aerospace Defense Command
NSIDC	National Snow and Ice Data Center
NetCDF	Network Common Data Format
PRF	Pulse Repetition Frequency
PSRF	Pixel Spatial Response Function
QSCAT	QuikSCAT and/or SeaWinds product
rSIR	radiometer version of SIR
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SCP	Scatterometer Climate Record Pathfinder
SDR	Sensor Data Record
Sigma-0	normalized radar cross section or backscatter (σ^0)
SIR	Scatterometer Image Reconstruction
SRF	Spatial Response Function
SWS	SeaWinds
TBD	To Be Determined
UTC	Coordinated Universal Time
VA	incidence-angle Variable Azimuth modulation coefficients
VV	Vertical-polarization transmit, Vertical-polarization receive

Figure 1: Illustration of the SeaWinds on QuikSCAT observation swath geometry. SeaWinds on ADEOS2 is similarly configured. VV-pol σ^o measurements are collected over a 1800 km swath, with HH-pol measurements collected over a 1400 km swath (Spencer et al., 2000, Perry, 2001).

3 Purpose of this Document

This document describes the CETB-compatible radar backscatter product “QuikSCAT/SeaWinds Scatterometer Twice-Daily SIR-Enhanced EASE-Grid 2.0 Radar Backscatter”, (NSIDC-078X, doi:TBD) created from 13.6 GHz SeaWinds Scatterometer observations collected during the QuikSCAT and SeaWinds missions.

The SeaWinds scatterometer flew on two spacecraft¹: the U.S. QuikSCAT (1999-2017) and the Japan Advanced Earth Observation System II (ADEOS2) (2003)². Using a scanning dual pencil-beam antenna, QuikSCAT and SeaWinds collected VV- and HH-polarized normalized radar cross section or radar backscatter (σ^o) at two incidence angles over a 1600 km wide swath (Fig. 1) at two simultaneous resolutions: eggs (footprint) at ~ 25 km resolution and slices at $\sim 6 \times 20$ km resolution (Spencer et al., 2003, Perry, 2001).

While designed and optimized for ocean wind observation, SeaWinds also collected

¹By JPL convention, SeaWinds on QuikSCAT is termed ‘QuikSCAT’ while SeaWinds on ADEOS2 is somewhat confusingly termed ‘SeaWinds’ (Perry, 2001).

²A third SeaWinds instrument known as RapidScat flew on the International Space Station (ISS) from Sept. 2014 through Aug. 2016. Since RapidScat only covered to $\pm 50^\circ$, it is not considered in this product (Paget et al., 2016).

σ^o measurements over land and ice. The observed σ^o depends on the surface roughness, observation geometry, and dielectric constant. These depend on geophysical parameters of interest, such as surface freeze/thaw state, snow and ice structure, moisture content, and vegetation characteristics, among others (Ulaby and Long, 2014). The QuikSCAT/SeaWinds image product ³ (*QSCAT*) provides a unique ‘snapshot’ view of the Earth’s surface during the two mission lifetimes (Long, 2017a).

The *QSCAT* product exploits the SeaWinds on QuikSCAT and ADEOS2 σ^o measurements to create a unique σ^o data set that captures the state of the Earth during the primary QuikSCAT era⁴ (1999-2009). To exploit this data, we employ image reconstruction techniques to create daily and twice-daily conventional and enhanced resolution images from the σ^o measurements. The σ^o new data set is provided to the science community to support cryosphere and climate studies.

³The *QSCAT* product includes separate QuikSCAT and SeaWinds images plus combined (Tandem) images.

⁴The QuikSCAT antenna quit spinning on DOY 327, 2009, which ended QuikSCAT’s primary ocean wind observation mission. However, the instrument kept operating in a fixed azimuth angle mode until 2017. This latter data is not included in this product.

4 Gridded and SIR-Enhanced Product Description

4.1 Product Description

The *QSCAT* product includes Level 1 gridded, twice-daily, radar backscatter data collected at 13.4 GHz for two radar channels (horizontal transmit-horizontal receive [HH] and vertical transmit-vertical receive [VV]). Data are gridded to the EASE-Grid 2.0 Azimuthal and Cylindrical projections (Brodzik et al., 2012, 2014), at two spatial resolutions, as described below. The *QSCAT* product is archived and distributed by the National Snow and Ice Data Center Distributed Active Archive Center (<https://nsidc.org/data/NSIDC-TBD/versions/1>).

Input data for the *QSCAT* v1.0 product are the QuikSCAT and SeaWinds L1B Sigma0 files (Perry, 2001) in hdf4 file format from JPL. Using the quality flags in the input data, only the highest quality measurements are included in *QSCAT* product. The product data coverage is global for the period beginning 14 Sept 1999 (DOY 257) through 28 June 2009 (DOY 179) for QuikSCAT and from 11 April 2003 (DOY 100) through 24 Oct 2003 (DOY 297) for SeaWinds and the tandem data. The original L1B σ^0 measurements are used with no additional calibration corrections applied to the data.

4.2 SeaWinds Instrument Background

The SeaWinds instruments aboard QuikSCAT and ADEOS2 are spaceborne scatterometers in near-polar sun-synchronous orbits (Spencer et al., 2000, Perry, 2001, Spencer et al., 2003). They collect measurements of the normalized radar cross-section (σ^0) of the Earth's surface. Over the oceans, these measurements are used to estimate the near-surface vector wind. Over the polar regions the backscatter measurements are useful for mapping melt, sea ice coverage, tracking icebergs, etc. (Long, 2017c). Because of its wide swath width and orbit geometry QuikSCAT and SeaWinds cover most areas in the polar regions multiple times per day. The high temporal sampling frequency in the polar regions makes QuikSCAT and SeaWinds powerful tools for studying geophysical processes in the polar regions.

Because QuikSCAT uses a conically scanning dual-pencil beam, the rotation of its parabolic reflector sweeps out circles on the Earth's surface centered around the nadir point of the satellite, see Fig. 1. (Technically, the pattern is a helix since the spacecraft nadir advances approximately 25 km during the antenna rotation.) There are two beams that sweep out in a conical scan, with one providing observations at approximately 46° and the other at 54.6° Earth incidence angle (EIA). Measurements from each of the two beams can be divided into two groups, forward-looking and aft-looking, defined by the antenna azimuth angle. Thus, a given point on the Earth's surface in the outer swath is observed twice by the VV-pol outer beam: once with the beam looking forward, and once with the beam looking backward. Within the inner swath, a given point is observed four times with two measurements, forward-looking and aft-looking, for each of the two beams. This observation scheme is es-

4.2 *SeaWinds Instrument Background Gridded and SIR-Enhanced Product Description*

essential to providing the azimuthal diversity required for wind retrieval (Ulaby and Long, 2014).

SeaWinds collects return echo power measurements, which are converted into σ^o using the radar equation (Perry, 2001, Spencer et al., 2003, Ulaby and Long, 2014, Long, 2017a). The σ^o value depends on the surface roughness, geometry, and dielectric constant (Ulaby and Long, 2014). The measured power P_r is the integral of the surface σ^o weighted by the measurement spatial response function (SRF) as described in Sec. 7.3. The SRF is largely defined by the two-way antenna pattern. Note that while a radiometer's footprint is defined by the antenna pattern, the radar footprint is defined by the antenna pattern squared due to the two-way travel of the signal from radar to the surface (Ulaby and Long, 2014). The nominal resolution of the footprint (egg) is described as nominally 25 km, though the effective resolution varies over the antenna rotation and orbit. Signal processing of the return echo divides the footprint into finer areas known as 'slices' (Perry, 2001, Spencer et al., 2003, Long, 2017a). Figure 2 illustrates the relative SRFs for eggs and slices as a function of the antenna rotation. Figure 3 provides a zoomed-in view of the response functions.

The QuikSCAT spacecraft flew in a sun-synchronous circular polar orbit at an inclination angle of 98.7° and an altitude of 800 km. Similarly, the ADEOS2 spacecraft flew in a sun-synchronous circular polar orbit at an inclination angle of 98.7° and an altitude of 900 km (Perry, 2001). During their mission lifetime, they had a 41 day near exact repeat orbit and a 4 day near-repeat orbit, collecting σ^o measurements essentially continuously on both sides of the spacecraft ground track. As described below, from these σ^o measurements two different twice-daily global images are created by (1) drop-in-the-bucket (DIB) gridding of the σ^o measurements and (2) applying the SIR algorithm to enhance the effective resolution of the data by exploiting the irregular patterns of measurement locations and signal oversampling (from overlaps in adjacent footprints and overlapping swaths). The enhanced resolution SIR images are reported on a 3.125 km grid, while the DIB images are reported on a 25 km grid.

4.2 SeaWinds Instrument Background Gridded and SIR-Enhanced Product Description

Figure 2: Illustration of (top row) egg and (bottom row) slice SRFs and how they vary as a function of antenna rotation angle for (left column) H-pol [the inner-beam] and (right column) V-pol [the outer-beam] measurements. Contours are shown at -3 dB from the peak response. For clarity, only contours are shown for slices that often overlap. For the purposes of visualization, the plots have been horizontally shifted to appear close together whereas they are actually very far apart. The jagged edges of the slice contours are the result of the quantized grid on which the SRF is evaluated.

Figure 3: More detailed illustration of the MRSF of a particular (left column) egg and (right column) slice measurements for (top row) H-pol and (bottom row) V-pol. The slices shown are from different measurements that happened to cover the same small box area (the small filled box). Contours are shown at -3, -6, -9 and -12 dB from the peak response. The image area is $100 \text{ km} \times 100 \text{ km}$. The large square box is 22.25 km. The small box is 2.225 km. For clarity, slices are offset from the center as indicated by the positions of the small squares.

Figure 4: A fall QuikSCAT Arctic σ^o (in dB) images. (left) Typical one-day v-pol image made with all passes in one day. (center) Same image masked to show the coverage of a single pass. (right) Same image masked to show the coverage of two consecutive passes. (Note: these images show only part of the standard EASE-2.0 Grid Northern Hemisphere projection area used for the standard QSCAT product.)

5 QuikSCAT and SeaWinds Sampling

This section introduces specifics of QuikSCAT and SeaWinds spatial-temporal sampling and the impact this has on the LTOD sampling. First, consider polar coverage. Figure 4 shows an Arctic QuikSCAT σ^o image created by averaging⁵ σ^o measurements from a single full UTC day of data, a single pass and two passes. Note that the North pole is in the center of the image. Because the transition point from ascending to descending occurs at the northernmost point in the satellites travel, roughly half of each is ascending and half descending. The second pass is much like the first, but rotated about the pole by some angle due to the rotation of the Earth under the satellite orbit. The second pass overlaps the first pass near the pole but is non-overlapping south of about 60°N.

As noted previously, QSCAT provides multiple passes per day in the polar regions. When combining multiple passes, it is useful to organize the data by the natural temporal divisions in the sensor coverage. For example, a common approach used with other sensors is to separately combine ascending and descending orbit passes. This works well at low latitudes because the ascending and descending passes are separated by roughly 12 hours, with each pass occurring at approximately the same local time of day (LTOD). However, at high latitudes this simple ascending/descending division scheme exhibits several undesirable features that degrade the effective temporal resolution.

⁵Actually, this image was created using the Scatterometer Image Reconstruction (SIR) algorithm that provides enhanced spatial resolution. It exploits overlap in the spatial measurement response function of the individual measurements for multiple passes to create enhanced spatial resolution σ^o images (Long, 2017a).

5.1 Time Division

The SeaWinds instruments flew in a near-polar sun-synchronous orbit at an altitude of approximately 800 km. Sun-synchronous satellites are unique because they pass over a given point on the earth's surface at nearly the same local time for any particular ascending or descending pass. In other words, sun-synchronous satellites maintain a constant angle to the sun, so measurements are always made at a similar local time of day. Having a 6:00 AM ascending node, QuikSCAT crosses the equator northbound at roughly 6:00 AM local time, and again southbound at 6:00 PM local time. The 1800 km wide swath spans approximately 16° of longitude at the equator, which corresponds to a LTOD variation over the swath of slightly over an hour since the LTOD varies by 15° per hour, or 360°/24 hr.

In the polar regions, lines of longitude are close together and the local time variation is rapid, so that as the satellite transitions from ascending to descending in the Arctic or from descending to ascending in the Antarctic, the satellite transitions through 12 hours of LTOD very quickly at high latitudes. This local time transition is common to all sun-synchronous satellite orbits.

At Ku-band, the operating band of the SeaWinds instruments, the radar backscatter of a natural surface is a strong function of the state of the water it contains, i.e., frozen or thawed. As a result of the sun-synchronous orbit geometry, the radar observations at a given location on the earth fall within two narrow diurnal windows. At the equator, these correspond to the ascending and descending orbit passes. Near the poles, the temporal windows widen but remain relatively narrow. Since surface temperatures can fluctuate widely during the day, simple daily averaging is problematic in the polar regions since it smears diurnal temperature fluctuations in the averaged σ^o . However, noting that there are two distinct local time windows, it becomes reasonable to split the data into two distinct images per day, using intervals based on LTOD. This minimizes the fluctuations in the observed σ^o due to changes in physical temperature from daily temperature cycling.

By convention, the time measurements collected on board the spacecraft are specified in UTC. The LTOD of a particular measurement at the measurement location is UTC time shifted by the the longitude of location. Note that the LTOD at the prime meridian (0° longitude) is the same as the UTC time. The LTOD of locations east of the prime meridian are earlier, while locations west of the prime meridian are later. To give a specific example, consider UTC and LTOD specified in fractional hours. LTOD can be computed as

$$LTOD_{\text{raw}} = UTC - longitude * 24/360 \quad (1)$$

where *longitude* is given in degrees, typically 0° to 360° or -180° to 180°. Note that for one 24-hour UTC day, the computed $LTOD_{\text{raw}}$ values can be negative or greater than 24 hours. This has important implications discussed below. Since the computation can result in $LTOD_{\text{raw}}$ values greater than 24 or less than zero, the final LTOD value is computed modulo 24. As noted previously, many geophysical processes depend on solar illumination,

Figure 5: *QuikSCAT swath coverage near the North pole illustrating the transition from morning pass to evening pass. The pole is in the center. The lines radiating out from the center depict hourly boundaries. (left) Dark blue indicates measurements flagged as Ascending in the L1B data, while yellow denotes measurements flagged as Descending. The beige area contains both ascending- and descending-flagged measurements. (right) Idealized ascending/descending flagging of individual measurements, which in this case corresponds to LTOD division.*

and thus on the LTOD. Hence, knowing and properly treating the LTOD of the measurements is important.

Recall that the sensors employ rotating antenna beams which sweep out a circle which becomes an overlapping helix due to the spacecraft motion along the nadir track. When the satellite reaches its most northern point the pass transitions from ascending to descending (Long, 2017a). Before this occurs the satellite measures forward from that transition point, and after the transition the satellite continues to measure aft of that transition point. This causes a disk-shaped region where the forward-looking measurements are still ascending, but the aft-looking measurements descending.

5.1.1 Day Boundary Effects

Perhaps the greatest limitation of using separate ascending and descending images to provide temporal resolution in the polar regions is the effect of day boundaries. The day boundary-affected region is the region of the image where data separated by nearly 24 hours is averaged together. Current polar QuikSCAT SIR images are created from one twenty-four

Figure 6: Average UTC time of day in mins for (left) ascending and (right) descending passes for day of year (DOY) 258, 2003. Note the areas of confused time of day to swath overlap that are widely spaced in time.

hour time period. All valid data taken during that twenty-four hour period is used to create the images. We note there are significant portions of the Arctic and Antarctic where the first several passes and the last several passes of each day cover the same area for ascending and descending images, due to the wide swath. Figure 6 shows average time images from QuikSCAT that show the areas where the first and last passes overlap. This day boundary-affected region is especially damaging to temporal resolution, because data separated by nearly twenty-four hours is averaged together.

The effects of the day boundary swath overlap are even more apparent in Figure 7. This image shows the time between the ascending and descending images. This difference image shows both positive and negative time separation, because the ascending image precedes the descending image in some regions, while in others descending image precedes the ascending image. The day boundary is the region of the image that separates the ascending-first region with the descending-first region. In general, the apparent (average) time separation is low across the entire day boundary affected region. In the day boundary affected region, the variance of time separation is also much larger than in the zones unaffected by day boundaries. The high variance limits the data utility for studies of time of day effects.

The effects of a day boundary are unavoidable in images made with shorter than daily temporal resolution because the satellite's sun-synchronous near polar orbit and wide swath, but are even more complicated when trying to combine data from multiple days.

Figure 7: Image showing the difference in time of day of the ascending and descending passes in Fig. 6. Time separation in minutes – descending first is positive.

5.1.2 Polar Swath Overlap

Figure 5 is a diagram illustrates how the measurements of a single pass of the outer beam are divided into ascending and descending passes. Note that the ascending/descending flag reported in the data is based on the satellite nadir position and does not take into account the rotation of the antenna. Thus, there is an overlap region of measurements flagged ascending with those flagged descending. This region of pass overlap is a primary cause for temporal resolution loss in ascending/descending images due to the overlap area that measurements separated by only a few minutes. The resulting images share temporally overlapping data and thus suffer from diminished temporal resolution. In contrast, when the data is divided by LTOD or proper ascending/descending, the division is appropriately sharp.

Figure 5 also illustrates the local time transition that occurs in the Arctic region. Note the wide span of local time hours along the swath. Because the disk-shaped region of overlap for each pass is closely located to the poles, it covers many lines of longitude and thus has a large variation in LTOD.

Figure 10 shows the number of passes over each pixel for nine consecutive passes. Because the satellite orbits the earth every 100 minutes, the daily averaged σ^0 SIR images include data from roughly 14.25 consecutive passes, repeating the same coverage pattern every 4 days. Figure 10 also shows another interesting feature: after only nine passes the first and the last passes are already starting to overlap, seen on the right side of the image. The overlap shown is a result of the satellite passing roughly the same location twice a day, and is what makes twice-daily full coverage images of the Arctic and Antarctic possible.

The other graphics in Fig. 10 show the number of passes over each pixel that nine con-

Figure 8: Maps of raw LTOD over the Southern Hemisphere within a particular single UTC day (10 Jan 2000) extending northward to 60°S in a polar stereographic projection with the pole at the center. Each left/right panel pair shows morning and evening LTODs. Yellow indicates that the raw LTOD is within the UTC day. Green indicates that the raw LTOD is prior to the UTC day. Brown indicates that raw LTOD is after the end of the UTC day. Compare with Fig. 9. (upper left) First pass of day. Note that the data (at 00:00 UTC) begins near the pole and extends to the right, moving from evening LTOD to morning LTOD. (upper right) Second pass of day. (center left) Third pass of day. (center right) Fourth pass of day. (lower left) Fifth pass of day. (lower right) Last pass of day, which ends just before the pole.

Figure 9: Maps of raw LTOD over the Northern Hemisphere within a particular single UTC day (10 Jan 2000) extending southward to $60^{\circ}N$ in a polar stereographic projection with the pole at the center. Compare with Fig. 8. (upper left) First pass of day. (evening precedes morning) (upper right) Second pass of day. (center left) Third pass of day. (center right) Fourth pass of day. (lower left) Fifth pass of day. (lower right) Last pass of day.

Figure 10: Coverage images that show how nine consecutive passes of QuikSCAT overlap in the Arctic for (left) full passes (ascending and descending), (center) only the swath portions flagged as ascending, and (right) only the swath portions flagged as descending passes. Pixel color shows the number of swath passes over that pixel.

secutive passes make separated into ascending and descending pass images respectively. The rounded edges on each of the ascending and descending passes are a direct result of the disk-shaped overlap region illustrated in Fig. 5.

The effect of the overlap regions is further illustrated the swath counts at each pixel as shown in Fig. 10. Note that over a large portion of the high latitude region (i.e., $>75^\circ$ N), there are seven swath passes over any given pixel in a 24 hr period. Because of the disk-shaped regions of overlap, in the high latitude region, pixels in the ascending image are sampled by five or six passes, and the descending image pixels are also sampled by five to six passes. In the overlap region there is very little information in the ascending image that is not also in the descending image.

Since surface temperatures can fluctuate during the day resulting in different melt, and therefore different backscatter, conditions from pass to pass, daily averaging of measurements is problematic since the averaging tends to smear diurnal variations in σ° . However, it is reasonable to split the data into two distinct intervals per day using intervals based on LTOD. Within each interval all the measurements occur at similar LTOD. Averaging within the interval minimizes the fluctuations in the observed σ° at high latitudes due to changes in physical temperature from daily temperature cycling. This provides twice-daily sampling into morning and evening passes based on observation LTOD. At low latitudes (i.e., near the equator), LTOD division is exact and is equivalent to ascending/descending division.

To illustrate how the QuikSCAT measurements fall into two distinct LTOD windows, consider the histograms of the LTOD of the measurements falling within two narrow high-latitude bands shown in Fig. 11. Note how the LTOD falls within one of two tight groups that correspond to the ascending and descending orbit passes, and that there are natural

Figure 11: Histograms of the LTOD of QuikSCAT egg σ^o measurements within a 1° latitude band centered at (left) 30°S , (center) 60°S , and (right) 70°S for a 24 hr period. (Northern hemisphere distributions are similar). Dashed red lines show division lines at 00:00 and 12:00 h.

Figure 12: Two-dimensional histograms of the LTOD of QuikSCAT egg σ^o measurements within a 1° latitude band centered at (left) 30°S , (center) 60°S , and (right) 70°S versus longitude for a 24 hr period. (Northern hemisphere distributions are similar). Dashed red lines show division lines at 00:00 and 12:00 h.

divisions in the measurement LTOD at 00:00 and 12:00 hrs. Thus, the measurements provide twice-daily sampling. Figure 12 presents a histogram of the LTOD versus longitude. The angled slopes result from the 1800 km swaths that span a range of LTOD as it passes through the latitude band. These same plots are shown for SeaWinds in Figs. 13 and 14. For SeaWinds, the LTOD division lines are at 04:00 and 16:00 hrs.

Note that when QuikSCAT and SeaWinds measurements are combined in a “tandem mission”, there are effectively three sample periods per day. Figure 15 compares the LTOD of QuikSCAT, SeaWinds, and tandem mission observations at high latitudes in the Northern and Southern Hemispheres. Note that there are three natural groupings of the measurements. In the Northern Hemisphere, the division lines are at midnight, 08:00, and 16:00 hrs while in the Southern Hemisphere the division lines are at 04:00, 12:00, and 20:00 hrs. Dividing the data this way provides three temporal samples per day, which provides resolu-

Figure 13: Histograms of the LTOD of SeaWinds egg σ^o measurements within a 1° latitude band centered at (left) 30°S , (center) 60°S , and (right) 70°S for a 24 hr period. (Northern hemisphere distributions are similar). Dashed red lines show QuikSCAT division lines at 00:00 and 12:00 hrs. Dashed green lines show SeaWinds division lines at 04:00 and 16:00 hrs. Compare Fig. 11.

tion of diurnal cycles such as freeze/thaw. When targeting the polar regions, given the short duration (DOY 100-370, 2003) of SeaWinds on ADEOS2 mission and the limited diurnal variability in the Antarctic winter, the trinary sampling during the tandem mission is likely to be on helpful only in the Northern Hemisphere.

5.2 Orbital Drift

Figures 8 and 9 illustrate the temporal progression of the raw LTOD of each polar pass in the Southern and Northern Hemispheres, respectively, for a single UTC day. On this day (10 Jan 2000), the data begins and ends near the South Pole, which can be seen in Fig. 8. Note that location of the beginning and end of the data shifts around. This is illustrated in Fig. 16 which shows the difference in the longitude of the ascending node between orbits 4 days apart. During the 20,000 orbits (about 1400 days or just under 4 years), the orbit drift in the longitude of ascending node slowly increased from 0° per 4 day period to about $0.25^\circ/\text{day}$ (1 deg per 4 day period), where it stabilized. Thus, the orbit is not quite “frozen”. This provides further rationale for using LTOD for day division.

Figure 14: Two-dimensional histograms of the LTOD of SeaWinds egg σ^o measurements within a 1° latitude band centered at (left) 30°S , (center) 60°S , and (right) 70°S versus longitude for a 24 hr period. (Northern hemisphere distributions are similar). Dashed red lines show QuikSCAT division lines at 00:00 and 12:00 hrs. Dashed green lines show SeaWinds division lines at 04:00 and 16:00 hrs. Compare Fig. 12.

Figure 15: Histograms of the LTOD of (left column) QuikSCAT, (center column) SeaWinds, and (right column) tandem mission (combined QuikSCAT and SeaWinds) egg σ^o measurements within a 1° latitude band centered at (top row) 70°S and (bottom row) 70°N for a 24 hr period. Dashed red lines show QuikSCAT division lines at 00:00 and 12:00 hrs. Dashed green lines show SeaWinds division lines at 04:00 and 16:00 hrs.

Figure 16: Difference in the longitude of the ascending node of orbits exactly 4 days apart during most of QuikSCAT's nominal wind mission. Spikes are the result of orbits when QuikSCAT was not operating.

6 Morning and Evening LTOD Division

Since there is such variation in local sample time across the wide swath of QuikSCAT and SeaWinds in the polar regions, separating the daily data can be readily accomplished by using the local times of the samples themselves rather than the reported ascending/descending flag, i.e., two specified local times of day are used as a decision boundaries. By separating the data according to local time of day, we can guarantee that all temporally similar samples are grouped into the same image.

Since QuikSCAT has a 6:00 AM ascending node and a 6:00 PM descending node a logically intuitive approach is to set the time boundaries at 12:00 AM, and 12:00 PM. As shown previously in Fig. 5, these boundaries correspond to a line perpendicular to the spacecraft's travel, almost exactly through the point where the spacecraft transitions from ascending to descending and vice versa. This solves the LTOD division question, but determining the optimum 24 hour averaging period remains.

6.1 Temporal Resolution Example

To illustrate how using LTOD averages versus UTC or ascending/descending flags can affect the effective temporal resolution, a simple experiment illustrating a rapid freeze/thaw event is considered. Figure 17 shows three consecutive days of spatially- and temporally-averaged QuikSCAT egg σ^o measurements whose center falls with 25 km of a particular location (84.0468 N 135.3773 W). The top and bottom plots display how the morning/evening method compares with the ascending/descending method. Individual passes are seen as nearly vertical columns of data, because the measurements are separated at most by a few minutes. In the ascending/descending scatter plot of the data samples, the effect of ascending and descending pass overlap described previously is shown: both ascending and descending data samples are found in satellite passes spread over a 6 hour period daily. As expected, the morning/evening method, which uses the local time directly to separate the data, shows the transient behavior of the measurements, and increases the effective separation times between the two daily images as well. The LTOD morning/evening averages provide better representation of the data, i.e., the LTOD method provides the best temporal sampling resolution.

The resulting improvement of temporal resolution in morning/evening images over using the ascending/descending flag is due to the temporal grouping of data. A change in the shape of the apparent swath as it reaches its northern apex is a direct result. Figure 5 mentioned previously shows how the swath is divided in the new method. Contrast this diagram with Fig. 5, which shows how the swath was separated for the ascending/descending method. The sharp division results in a pattern illustrated by Fig. 18, that shows the geometry of several consecutive passes separated by local time into morning and evening images.

Using the local time of day as the decision rule for separating the data and creating SIR

Figure 17: Timeseries plot comparing the ascending/descending method (top) of data segregation and the new morning/evening method (bottom) (84.0468 N 135.3773 W from DOY 163 to DOY 166, 2003). Note the morning/evening method follows transients better and is closer to uniform samples.

images has the added benefit of controlling and relegating the day boundary affected region to a small portion of the image. Intuitively, the LTOD filter places this region right over 180° longitude, at or near the international date line. The day boundary affected region is only as wide as the antenna footprint coverage area, an area several pixels in width.

The morning/evening images have a clear line visible along the 180° longitude line, which is the result of the day boundary at this location. This does have some negative repercussions. For one, the boundary line clearly appears as an anomaly as the data transitions a twenty-four hour temporal discontinuity. This anomaly may negatively affect certain studies of ice movement in this portion of the world, making it more difficult to track the ice's movement across this day boundary without taking this into account.

Figure 18: Count of number of passes from seven consecutive passes overlap in (left) morning and (right) evening data in the Arctic. Pixel color shows the number of swaths that passed over each pixel. Compare with Fig. 10.

6.2 LTOD Over Multiple Days

To aid in interpretation of the polar σ^o values, separate daily images of the morning and evening passes can be created. These provide twice-daily temporal sampling. Within each image only σ^o values collected within the same LTOD interval are combined. Since the raw LTOD times for data collected during a since UTC do not meet this criteria, some data from the UTC data before and/or after the target LTOD data needs to be included, with data from the current UTC included in multiple LTOD days.

Note that the LTOD day boundary is set (chosen) to be the international dateline. This extends from the pole upward in the Northern Hemisphere plots and from the pole downward in the Southern Hemisphere plots.

Consider the lower right panel of Fig. 19. In creating a evening LTOD image for the data, all of the yellow data is used. However, the green data corresponds to an LTOD from the previous LTOD day. Hence, it is not used. Instead, the similar data from the first 4 revs of the next UTC data are used. This data has closer LTOD. Thus the LTOD evening “day” includes data from the two UTC days. The LTOD data used extends from several hours after the start of the UTC day to several hours after. This is a natural LTOD boundary condition. The morning LTOD day is potentially a little trickier. Applying the same logic, data from the last few hours of the previous data through to within 4 hours of the end of the day are used. However, it is convenient to adjust the LTOD days to always start on the similarly numbered UTC day of the year. To do this, the data usage interval is started near the end of

Figure 19: Maps of raw LTOD over the equatorial region within a particular single UTC day (10 Jan 2000). (left) Shows morning while (right) shows evening raw LTOD labeling. Yellow indicates that the raw LTOD is within the UTC day. Green indicates that the raw LTOD is prior to the UTC day. Brown indicates that raw LTOD is after the end of the UTC day. The prime meridian in the center with latitude extending $\pm 67^\circ$. Compare to Figs. 8 and 9.

the UTC (the brown area) and extended into the next day, i.e., the yellow area of the next UTC day, and ending at the brown area of the next day. Using this convention, the evening LTOD uses data mostly from the corresponding UTC whereas the morning LTOD uses data mostly from the next UTC. (This same description applies to both hemisphere.)

The previous discussion applies to a single day. What should be done when multiple days are combined? Using the convention just described, a multiple day LTOD images corresponding to days d_1 to d_2 should start during UTC d_1 but include data from UTC $d_2 + 1$, with the amount depending on whether it is a morning or evening LTOD.

Consider now the raw LTOD labeling developed for polar passes when shown in an equatorial view, see Fig. 19. Note, however, that there is no need to use the LTOD scheme for equatorial data since ascending/descending flags are equivalent to LTOD division. There is no need for differentiating LTOD periods and UTC day periods.

6.3 Grid Spatial Extent

Azimuthal QSCAT grids extend to the full Northern (EASE2-N) and Southern (EASE2-S) hemispheres (Fig. 20), as described in Brodzik et al. (2012, 2014). The spatial extent of the equal-area cylindrical projections (Fig. 21 and Fig. 22) is defined to match the extent of compatible grids favored by two user communities: (1) the Mid-Latitude (EASE2-M) grid, extending to $\pm 85.044\ 566\ 4^\circ$ latitude, has been adopted by the SMAP user community.

Figure 20: Northern and Southern EASE-Grid 2.0 projection extents. The land-ocean mask is from Brodzik and Knowles (2011).

Figure 21: Cylindrical EASE-Grid 2.0 projection extents. Full extent coverage is EASE2-M, with horizontal red lines delineating the smaller latitudinal extent of the EASE2-T grid. The land-ocean mask is from Brodzik and Knowles (2011).

Figure 22: Relationship of EASE-Grid 2.0 cylindrical projection extents. The EASE2-T extent is defined for compatibility with the CETB products. (Difference in latitudinal extent is exaggerated, see Fig. 21 for actual difference in projected extent (Brodzik et al., 2021).

And, (2) the Temperate and Tropical (EASE2-T) grid, limited to latitudes equatorward of $\pm 67.1^\circ$, is consistent with the original CETB products defined for similar scanning radiometers (Brodzik et al., 2021)(Brodzik et al., 2016) and radars (Long and Miller, 2022). See Appendix A Table 7 for grid specifications.

6.4 Grid Spatial Resolution

QSCAT grid resolutions are defined relative to a 25 km base resolution, i.e., 25 km and 3.125 km MEaSURES CETB data products (Brodzik et al., 2021). Nested resolutions relative to the CETB 25 km base grids are defined using exact divisors of 2, as illustrated in Figure 23. QSCAT projection extents, dimensions and grid cell size details are included in Appendix A. Grids used for QSCAT processing are included in Table 4.

Figure 23: CETB nested grids based on a 25 km base resolution. Only 25 km and 3.125 km divisions are used in QSCAT products (Long et al., 2019).

Table 4: QSCAT EASE-Grid 2.0 base grids produced by the projection and reconstruction algorithm. See Section 7 for GRD and SIR reconstruction details.

EASE2-M	EASE2-N	EASE2-S	EASE2-T
n/a	25km (GRD)	25km (GRD)	25km (GRD)
n/a	3.125km (GRD/SIR)	3.125km (GRD/SIR)	3.125km (GRD/SIR)

6.5 Data Products

The QSCAT product at the NSIDC DAAC is global and covers the period beginning 14 Sept 1999 (DOY 257) through 28 June 2009 (DOY 179) for QuikSCAT and from 11 April 2003 (DOY 100) through 24 Oct 2003 (DOY 297) for SeaWinds and the tandem data. No calibration corrections were applied to the data. In creating a time series, a “moving average” approach was used with overlapping imaging periods that start every mission day and extend through the desired 1- or 2-day period (or to the end of the mission, whichever comes first). The 4-day images start every other day. Tables 5 and 6 summarize the available QSCAT products, which are all in CETB-standard EASE-2 Grid projections.

Table 5: Available twice-daily QuikSCAT image products. (1999-2009)

Type	days	Algo- rithm	Pix. Res. (km)	Regions*	Polar- ations	LTOD All/N,S/T	Size [†] N/S/T (MB)
eggs	1,2,4	GRD	25	N,S,T	HH,VV	B/M,E/A,D	2.2/2.3/4
eggs	1,2,4	SIR	3.125	N,S,T	HH,VV	B/M,E/A,D	124/124/224
slices	1,2,4	GRD	25	N,S,T	HH,VV	B/M,E/A,D	2.2/2.3/4
slices	1,2,4	AVE	3.125	N,S,T	HH,VV	B/-/-	320/320/460
slices	1,2,4	SIR	3.125	N,S,T	HH,VV	B/M,E/A,D	160/160/285

* Region code: N=Northern Hemisphere, S=Southern Hemisphere, T=Global

† Uncompressed size

Table 6: Available thrice-daily tandem (QuikSCAT and SeaWinds) image products. (2003 only)

Type	days	Algo- rithm	Pix. Res. (km)	Regions*	Polar- ations	LTOD All/N,S/T	Size [†] N/S/T (MB)
eggs	1,2,4	GRD	25	N,S,T	HH,VV	B/M,E,N/A,D	2.2/2.3/4
eggs	1,2,4	SIR	3.125	N,S,T	HH,VV	B/M,E,N/A,D	124/124/224
slices	1,2,4	GRD	25	N,S,T	HH,VV	B/M,E,N/A,D	2.2/2.3/4
slices	1,2,4	AVE	3.125	N,S,T	HH,VV	B/-/-	320/320/460
slices	1,2,4	SIR	3.125	N,S,T	HH,VV	B/M,E,N/A,D	160/160/285

* Region code: N=Northern Hemisphere, S=Southern Hemisphere, T=Global

† average filecd size

7 Algorithm Description

7.1 Background

The *effective resolution* of an image is defined by the *pixel spatial response function* (PSRF), where the effective resolution is given by the dimension(s) of the one-half power (3-dB) extent of the PSRF (Long, 2017a). In contrast, the *measurement spatial response function* (SRF) describes the spatial characteristics of the *individual* measurements. For a radar, the SRF depends on the two-way antenna gain pattern, the scan geometry, and the signal processing. For both radars and radiometers, the PSRF depends on the SRF and the image formation algorithm. In a linear image formation algorithm, the reported pixel value consists of the weighted sum of nearby measurements. In this case the PSRF is then the normalized weighted sum of the measurement SRF functions, including their spatial offset from the center of the pixel. Examples of SeaWinds SRFs and PSRF are available in Long (2017a).

The spacing of pixels is termed the “pixel posting” or the “posting resolution”. In creating the QSCAT backscatter image product, multiple measurements from different passes are combined into single pixel values. The resulting image pixels have an effective resolution slightly coarser than the posting resolution since (1) the measurements are not all centered the same, and (2) their SRFs can extend outside of the pixel area. The PSRF provides the tool for defining the effective pixel resolution (Long and Brodzik, 2016a). In order to be compatible with the CETB data set, two posting resolutions are considered: 25 km and 3.125 km, see Fig. 24. The former is reserved for GRD products while the finer resolution is used for the resolution-enhanced products.

7.2 QSCAT Backscatter Image Products

The QSCAT backscatter products include both low-noise (low-resolution) coarse resolution GRD images and higher-noise (enhanced) fine-resolution (SIR) images. The various products have their advantages and disadvantages. Multiple image types allow users the flexibility of choosing the appropriate images for their research application.

To create radar CETB-compatible products, different approaches are used for each resolution. Because the sensor was not designed as an imager, there are gaps between the measurements that must be filled by combining multiple passes over an extended imaging period. As a result of the 4 day near-repeat cycle, two imaging periods are defined: 2 day and 4 day. These provide a user-selectable tradeoff between temporal resolution, spatial resolution, and noise.

For GRD images, the source backscatter measurements are gridded onto a 25 km grid using DIB techniques. In this approach, all the measurements whose center location falls within a grid element are averaged into the reported value. For the 3.125 km product, the

Figure 24: Conceptual illustration of coarse 25 km (left) vs. high resolution 3.125 km (right) pixels. The ellipses represent the individual SRFs of the egg measurements. DIB is used for GRD images while AVE and SIR are used for high resolution images.

source measurements are processed using the first iteration of the SIR algorithm (AVE). AVE images use weighted averages where the weighting is the measurement SRF, which may vary from measurement to measurement. Along with each measurement's SRF, the SIR algorithm exploits the irregular patterns of the measurement locations and signal oversampling from overlaps in adjacent footprints and overlapping passes. Table 5 summarizes the image product types.

7.3 Radar Spatial Response and Image Reconstruction

The effective spatial resolution of an image product is determined by the SRF of the sensor and by the image formation algorithm used. As previously noted, the SRF is determined by the antenna gain pattern, the scan geometry (notably the antenna scan angle), and the signal processing, see Long et al. (1993) and Long (2017a). The SRF of QuikSCAT and SeaWinds measurements are illustrated in Figs. 2 and 3. The goal in forming a σ^o image is to estimate the backscatter properties of the surface from noisy measurements that employ (possibly variable) MSFs that sample the surface. Though simple to implement, DIB techniques ignore the SRF, which limits their effective resolution. Reconstruction techniques that use the SRF can provide much finer effective resolution (Long, 2017a).

Reconstruction processing techniques effectively assume the underlying signal (the backscatter) being sampled is band-limited, which is the only consistent assumption possible with sampled data (Long and Brodzik, 2016b, Long and Franz, 2016b). For reconstruction, the backscatter at each point of a fine-scale pixel grid is estimated, producing a backscatter image or map. While the image is generated on a regular grid, the measurement loca-

tions and MRF are not aligned with the grid, and so the measurements form an irregular sampling pattern, which can complicate signal reconstruction. Many commonly used image formation algorithms either ignore this (as is done in DIB) or attempt to interpolate or distance-weight the measurements values. In using image reconstruction, we avoid these ad hoc, non-optimal approaches and explicitly compute the MRF of each measurement as part of the reconstruction process. This is computationally intense, but provides the best possible image construction. The remainder of this section outlines this process.

An individual scatterometer backscatter measurement z_i can be modeled as the integral of the product of the SRF and the surface backscatter, i.e.,

$$z_i = \iint \text{SRF}_i(x, y; pp) \sigma^o(x, y, \theta, \phi_i, t, pp) dx dy + \text{noise} \quad (2)$$

where $\text{SRF}_i(x, y; pp)$ is the spatial SRF of the i^{th} measurement at x, y , and the surface σ^o depends on spatial location x, y , incidence angle θ , azimuth angle ϕ , time t , and polarization pp , i.e.,

$$\text{SRF}_i(x, y; pp) = \iint \frac{G_a^2(x, y; pp) G_p(x, y; pp)}{R^4(x, y)}. \quad (3)$$

where

$$X = \iint \frac{G_a^2(x, y; pp) G_p(x, y; pp)}{R^4(x, y)} dx dy. \quad (4)$$

where $G_a(x, y; pp)$ is the effective two-way antenna gain at the surface at (x, y) for polarization pp , $G_p(x, y; pp)$ is the processor gain, and $R(x, y)$ is the slant range from the radar to the surface. Note that the measurement is an average of σ^o in spatial coordinates as well as in azimuth and incidence angles.

Eq. 2 is discretized on the imaging grid to become

$$z_i = \sum_{j \in \text{image}} h_{ij} a_j + \text{noise} \quad (5)$$

where a_j is the backscatter at the center of the j^{th} pixel at (x_l, y_k) and $h_{ij} = \text{SRF}(x_l, y_k; \phi_i)$ is the discretely sampled SRF for the i -th measurement evaluated at the j -th pixel center where h_{ij} is normalized so that $\sum_j h_{ij} = 1$. In practice, the SRF is negligible some distance from the measurement center, so the sums need only be computed over a small area around the pixel. Ignoring the noise, Eq. 5 can be written as the matrix equation

$$\vec{Z} = \mathbf{H} \vec{a} \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{H} contains the sampled SRF for each measurement and \vec{Z} and \vec{a} are vectors composed of the measurements z_i and a_j , respectively. Even for small images, \mathbf{H} is large and sparse, and may be over-determined or under-determined depending on the number and

locations of the measurements. Reconstruction of the surface σ^o is equivalent to inverting Eq. 6.

The iterative SIR algorithm (Early and Long, 2001, Long et al., 1993) is a particular reconstruction algorithm that is specifically developed for scatterometer image formation. SIR approximates a maximum-entropy solution to an under-determined equation and a least-squares solution to an over-determined system. The first iteration of SIR is termed ‘AVE’ (for weighted AVErage) and provides a simple reconstruction estimate that is refined in later SIR iterations. The AVE estimate of the j -th pixel is given by

$$a_j = \frac{\sum_i h_{ij} z_i}{\sum_i h_{ij}} \quad (7)$$

where the sums are over all measurements that have non-negligible SRF at the pixel. The SIR iteration begins with an initial image a_j^0 whose pixels are set to the AVE values defined in Eq. 7. Thereafter, the iterative equation for single-variate SIR is given by

$$a_j^{k+1} = \frac{\sum_i u_{ij}^k h_{ij}}{\sum_i h_{ij}} \quad (8)$$

where

$$u_{ij}^k = \begin{cases} \left[\frac{1}{2p_i^k} \left(1 - \frac{1}{d_i^k} \right) + \frac{1}{a_j^k d_i^k} \right]^{-1} & d_i^k \geq 1 \\ \frac{1}{2} p_i^k (1 - d_i^k) + a_j^k d_i^k & d_i^k < 1 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

$$d_i^k = \left(\frac{z_i}{p_i^k} \right)^\lambda \quad (10)$$

where $d_i^k = (s_i/p_i^k)^\lambda$ with $\lambda = \frac{1}{2}$. The factor d_i^k is the square root of the ratio of a measurement to its forward projection at the k^{th} iteration. The update term u_{ij}^k is a non-linear function of both d_i^k and the previous image a_j^k . The sigmoid-like non-linearity in Eq. 9 constrains the amount of change permitted during any one iteration, thereby minimizing the effects of noise (Long et al., 1993). A spatial median filter can be applied to the image between iterations to further reduce the noise (Long et al., 1993).

For scatterometers, SIR is implemented in dB (Long, 2017a, Early and Long, 2001, Long et al., 1993); i.e., the computation is done on $10 \log_{10}(z_i)$ rather than on the linear-space value z_i as done in the radiometer version of SIR (Long and Brodzik, 2016a, Long and Daum, 1998). In considering the differences between linear and dB processing, recall the well-known fact that computing the arithmetic mean of values in dB is equivalent to computing $10 \log_{10}$ of the geometric mean of the linear-space values (Wikipedia, 2016). With the measurements in dB, the reconstruction processing can be viewed as a form of weighted geometric mean filtering. Since it has been found that geometric mean filters are better at

Figure 25: Comparison of the effective PSRF of pixels for egg and slice image formation. For this illustrative example coarse grid is 22.5 km while the fine grid is 2.225 km. This example is for *H-pol*, but *V-pol* is similar. The size of each panel is 100 km \times 100 km. Linear gray scale. Contours are shown at -3, -6, -9, and -12 dB from the peak response. (Long, 2017a)

reducing Gaussian-type noise and preserving linear features than (linear) arithmetic mean filters (Pitas and Venetsanopoulos, 1986), some performance advantage to dB processing is expected and observed (Long, 2017a). The linear and dB computations yield similar, but slightly different results, due to the varying signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of the measurements and limited signal dynamic range (Long, 2017a).

In practice, since the σ^o measurements are quite noisy, attempting full image reconstruction can produce excessive noise enhancement. In general, more iterations improve the signal and resolution, but also increase the noise level. To reduce noise enhancement and resulting artifacts, regularization can be employed, at the expense of resolution (Long and Franz, 2016a, Early and Long, 2001, Long et al., 1993, Long, 2017a). Regularization is a smoothing constraint introduced in an inverse problem to prevent extreme values or over-fitting. Regularization results in partial or incomplete reconstruction of the signal (Long and Franz, 2016a). It also creates a trade off between signal reconstruction accuracy and noise enhancement. SIR includes regularization achieved by prematurely terminating the iteration. Based on simulations and confirmed by analysis of actual data, 20-30 iterations provides a nice trade off result Long (2017a). We note that for a noisy sensor like a

Figure 26: *Extracted QuikSCAT H-pol images created from four days (254-257, 1999) of data for different cases of algorithm. Scale in dB. Note the finer detail apparent in the SIR-enhanced images. (Long, 2017a)*

scatterometer, the results are not particularly sensitive to the precise value chosen, hence a fixed value can be selected. Selection of the number of iterations is based on simulation, see Early and Long (2001), Long et al. (1993) and Long (2017a). For this product, a fixed number (30) of SIR iterations is employed for both eggs and slices.

A comparison of the resulting PSRF of GRD, AVE, and SIR images for eggs and slices is shown in Fig. 25. Note that that SIR PSRF is significantly finer than the non-enhanced GRD and slice PSRFs. Figure 26 compares the resolution of the resulting images for a small area in Antarctica.

7.3.1 Local-Time-of-Day

As previously noted, the goal of image reconstruction is to estimate the surface σ^o from the sensor σ^o measurements. Measurements from multiple orbit passes over a narrow local time window are combined. When multiple measurements are combined, the resulting images represent a temporal average of the measurements over the averaging period. There is an implicit assumption that the surface characteristics remain constant over the imaging period for both conventional-resolution (GRD) and enhanced-resolution (SIR) images.

The radar backscatter of a natural surface is a strong function of the state of the water it contains, i.e., frozen or thawed (Ulaby and Long, 2014). As a result of the sun-synchronous orbit geometry, the radar observations at a given location on the earth fall within two narrow diurnal windows. At the equator, these correspond to the ascending and descending orbit passes. This can be exploited to provide twice-daily sampling. Thus, *QSCAT* images on the cylindrical *EASE-Grid 2.0* projections are separated by ascending and descending passes. A separate image (“both”) product is also made. It combines all data over the time period. This maximizes spatial coverage at the expense of temporal resolution.

Near the poles, the temporal windows widen to several hours but remain relatively narrow. Since surface temperatures can fluctuate widely during the day, daily averaging is not generally useful at these locations, since it smears diurnal temperature fluctuations in the averaged σ^o . However, it is reasonable to split the data into two distinct images per day, using intervals based on LTOD, thereby only combining measurements with a similar LTOD. This minimizes the fluctuations in the observed backscatter at high latitudes due to changes in physical temperature from daily temperature cycling.

The *QSCAT* images on the azimuthal projections are separated into twice-daily, morning and evening passes based on observation LTOD, in addition to images that combine the two. At low latitudes, which typically have few overlapping swaths at similar LTOD in the same day, LTOD division is equivalent to ascending/descending division. An ancillary data array is included in each file, to describe the effective time average of the measurements combined into the pixel for a particular day. This enables investigators to explicitly account for the LTOD temporal variation of the measurements included in a particular pixel.

7.4 Incidence Angle Effects

Over natural surfaces σ^o depends on the measurement incidence angle (EIA). Since SeaWinds is a pencil-beam system, it collects σ^o measurements at only two incidence angles: nominally 46° for the HH-pol inner beam and 54.1° for the outer VV-pol outer beam. No corrections are made for variations in incidence angle. This differs from fan-beam products which normalize the incidence angle to 40° , e.g., NSCATATBD, SASSATBD, ASCATATBD.

7.5 Azimuth Angle Effects

Periodic natural surfaces exhibit variations in σ^o with azimuth angle, including water waves (Ulaby and Long, 2014, Naderi et al., 1991), sastrugi and snow dunes (Long and Drinkwater, 2000, Lindsley and Long, 2016, Ashcraft and Long, 2006, Long and Miller, 2022). The measured σ^o is thus a function of the azimuth direction from which the surface is observed. Scatterometers such as SeaWinds are *designed* to make multi-azimuth observations over the ocean to exploit this effect for wind-driven waves in order to estimate the near-surface wind (Spencer et al., 2000, Naderi et al., 1991). However, these measurements are intrinsically coarse since they must be made in a single pass. Unlike the ocean, land and ice features do not (generally) change as rapidly so observations from multiple passes can be combined.

Over the course of the orbit's repeat cycle each point on the surface can be observed at multiple azimuth angles (Spencer et al., 2000). For example, as the spacecraft passes over a particular location within the swath, the location is first observed looking forward, then a short while later the same location is observed looking backward. Over the orbit repeat cycle, the ground track shifts so that the same location is observed from a different set of azimuth angles for each pass. The precise distribution of azimuth angles depends on the orbit latitude, with the narrowest range near the equator and the largest range at high latitudes.

Note that there is a trade off between the imaging time period, the spatial resolution, and the azimuth sampling (Long, 2017b). Short time periods provide better temporal resolution for tracking sea ice motion and rapid freeze thaw events. However, short time periods provide inadequate coverage and/or azimuth sampling to reliably estimate the azimuth angle variation, particularly when the data is divided by local time of day. Recalling that the orbit repeat cycle is near-repeat after 4 days, we choose $N_d = 4$ imaging intervals (N_d in days)⁶. The imaging intervals are chosen to overlap by $N_d - 1$ days so they act like a N_d long moving average filter. Shorter N_d provides finer temporal resolution at the expense of reduced spatial coverage/resolution, including possible spatial artifacts in the reconstruction. These negative effects are reduced for the longer imaging intervals.

Note that a particular σ^o observation is an average of σ^o in spatial coordinates as well

⁶Imaging intervals are specified in days, but may include only morning or evening (or descending or ascending) passes depending on the LTOD setting.

as in azimuth and incidence angles. Within a single measurement the azimuth angle span ($<1^\circ$) for a particular measurement is small and can be neglected. The incidence angle span within a single measurement can be slightly larger ($\sim 1-1.5^\circ$). The roll off of σ° versus incidence angle slightly biases the integrated measurement toward smaller incidence angles. However, this effect is neglected in the *QSCAT* product.

On the other hand, the variation in σ° as a function of azimuth and incidence angles for different measurements is important and provides useful geophysical information. Incidence angle variation is considered in the previous section. Of source, the variation in σ° as a function of azimuth enables wind retrieval over the ocean (Naderi et al., 1991, Ulaby and Long, 2014, Meissner et al., 2017). Azimuth variation (sometimes termed ‘azimuth modulation’) can be observed over snow dunes and sastrugi (Long and Drinkwater, 2000, Ashcraft and Long, 2006, Lindsley and Long, 2016) and sand dunes in ergs⁷ (Stephen and Long, 2007). As a result, significant azimuth variation in σ° is common over the Great Ice Sheets (GI) of Greenland and Antarctica, but is only rarely observed elsewhere over large regions with the exceptions of ergs.

Since each satellite pass observes a given point on the surface from a limited azimuth angle, the variation of σ° with azimuth can lead to biases in the mean σ° value and to imaging artifacts when multiple passes with different azimuth angle observations are combined. To deal with azimuth variation of σ° on the GI, previous investigators, e.g., Long and Drinkwater (2000) Ashcraft and Long (2006), and Lindsley and Long (2016), have used a simple Fourier series model for the azimuth variation observed in σ° . Two models have been considered (Long and Miller, 2022, 2023). Here, the fixed azimuth (FA) modulation coefficient model is used at a fixed incidence angle as determined by the beam polarization. The azimuth modulation model employed can be expressed as

$$\sigma^0 = A + M_1 \cos(\phi + P_1) + M_2 \cos(2\phi + P_2) \quad (11)$$

where ϕ is the azimuth angle, $M_1 = A_1$ and $M_2 = A_2$ for the FA model and P_1 and P_2 are the phase angles relative to north. Note that the model can be with σ° in dB or linear space, though dB models have proven to be the most successful (Long and Drinkwater, 2000, Lindsley and Long, 2016). Other azimuth modulation studies can be found in Ashcraft and Long (2006), Long and Drinkwater (2000), and Long and Miller (2022, 2023).

To illustrate the azimuth variation in the QuikSCAT/SeaWinds data, Fig. 27 show scatter density plots of the backscatter measurements over two study areas in the Greenland dry snow zone and in Antarctica versus azimuth angle. In these plots, a 1-2 dB azimuth modulation is apparent. The plots also illustrate the incomplete and variable density of the azimuth angle observations within the regions.

The PSRF is defined by the weighted combination of the MRFs of the measurements included in the pixel value. The weighting is determined by the choice of the algorithm

⁷An erg landform is a large region or ‘sea’ of vegetation-free, wind-swept desert sand.

Figure 27: Scatter density of QuikSCAT σ^0 in dB versus azimuth angle for two polar study regions. A second-order FA model fit to the data is shown as the light grey line. Data is from a single 4-day orbit repeat cycle on days DOY 10-13, 2005.

used to create the image (Long, 2017a). This summation can be done in linear space (i.e., not in dB) or in dB. As noted in Section 7.3, the latter is used for SIR. When multiple overlapping measurements are available, i.e., the surface is oversampled, it is possible to obtain images with finer effective resolution.

Enhancement of the effective resolution *requires* dense sampling of the surface. This is the reason multiple passes are used. In addition, multiple measurements at a diversity of incidence angles are required to estimate the incidence angle slope. When the surface is adequately sampled, the effective spatial resolution is improved, which can result in a reduction in noise. However, when the surface is undersampled, it is difficult for the image resolution to be much better than the SRF resolution.

7.6 Data Volume

Tables 5 and 6 summarize available CETB QSCAT radar products, which are all in CETB-standard EASE-2 Grid projections and netcdf4 file format. In this table, “days” refers to the length of time used for image formation. Imaging periods overlap, with a new image started each day. Note that for LTOD images that in order to have the right number of morning or evening passes, the time period of the measurements actually used in the images may extend slightly outside the multi-day period. Individual file sizes vary due to internal file compression for each image type. See Section 6.5 for access details.

8 Acknowledgements

This work utilizes resources from the Brigham Young University Scatterometer Climate Record Pathfinder and University of Colorado Boulder Research Computing Group, which is supported by the National Science Foundation (awards TBD), the University of Colorado Boulder and Colorado State University.

9 References

References

- Ashcraft, I. S. and D. G. Long. 2006. Relating microwave backscatter azimuth modulation to surface properties of the Greenland ice sheet. *Journal of Glaciology* 52(177), 257–266. doi:10.3189/172756506781828764.
- Brodzik, M., D. Long, M. Hardman, A. Paget, and R. Armstrong. 2016. MEaSURES calibrated enhanced-resolution passive microwave daily EASE-grid 2.0 brightness temperature ESDR, version 2. doi:https://doi.org/10.5067/MEASURES/CRYOSPHERE/NSIDC-0630.002.
- Brodzik, M. J., B. Billingsley, T. Haran, B. Raup, and M. H. Savoie. 2012. EASE-Grid 2.0: Incremental but significant improvements for Earth-gridded data sets. *International Society for Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing* 1, 32–45. doi:10.3390/ijgi101003.
- Brodzik, M. J., B. Billingsley, T. Haran, B. Raup, and M. H. Savoie. 2014. Correction: Brodzik, M.J., *et al.* EASE-Grid 2.0: Incremental but Significant Improvements for Earth-Gridded Data Sets, *ISPRS Int. J. Geo-Inf.* 2012, 1, 32–45. *ISPRS Int. J. Geo-Inf.* 3, 1154–1156. doi:10.3390/ijgi3031154.
- Brodzik, M. J. and K. Knowles. 2011. EASE-Grid 2.0 Land-Ocean-Coastline-Ice Masks Derived from Boston University MODIS/Terra Land Cover Data. NASA National Snow and Ice Data Center DAAC, Boulder, CO USA. Digital Media, <http://nsidc.org/data/nsidc-0610>, doi:https://doi.org/10.5067/XR8523MC24TB.
- Brodzik, M. J., D. G. Long, M. A. Hardman, A. Paget, and R. L. Armstrong. 2016, updated 2021. MEaSURES Calibrated Enhanced-Resolution Passive Microwave Daily EASE-Grid 2.0 Brightness Temperature ESDR, Version 1. National Snow and Ice Data Center, Boulder, CO USA. Digital Media, <http://nsidc.org/data/nsidc-0630>, doi:https://doi.org/10.5067/MEASURES/CRYOSPHERE/NSIDC-0630.001.
- Brodzik, M. J., J. M. Ramage, M. A. Hardman, D. G. Long, and R. L. Armstrong. 2018. Improving melt onset detection in mountainous regions from the new, enhanced-resolution passive microwave climate record. Poster presentation at EGU General Assembly, CR 2.1:10690, Vienna, Austria, 9–13 April.
- Early, D. S. and D. G. Long. 2001. Image reconstruction and enhanced resolution imaging from irregular samples. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* 39(2), 291–302. doi:10.1109/36.905237.

- Lindsley, R. and D. Long. 2016. ASCAT and QuikSCAT azimuth modulation of backscatter over East Antarctica. *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters*, 13(8), 1134–1138. doi:10.1109/LGRS.2016.2572101.
- Long, D. and M. Brodzik. 2016a. Optimum image formation for spaceborne microwave radiometer products. *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sensing* 54(5), 2763–2779. doi:10.1109/TGRS.2015.2505677.
- Long, D. and D. Daum. 1998. Spatial resolution enhancement of SSM/I data. *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sensing* 36(2), 407–417. doi:10.1109/36.662726.
- Long, D. and M. Drinkwater. 2000. Azimuth variation in microwave scatterometer and radiometer data over Antarctica. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* 38(4), 1857–1870. doi:10.1109/36.851769.
- Long, D. and R. Franz. 2016a. Band-limited signal reconstruction from irregular samples with variable apertures. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* 54(4), 2424–2436. doi:10.1109/TGRS.2015.2501366.
- Long, D., P. Hardin, and P. Whiting. 1993. Resolution enhancement of spaceborne scatterometer data. *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sensing* 31(3), 700–715. doi:10.1109/36.225536.
- Long, D. and J. Z. Miller. 2022. SMAP radar SAR and SIR-enhanced twice-daily EASE-grid 2.0 radar backscatter. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5067/SCKWZSWQ7HPL>.
- Long, D. and J. Z. Miller. 2023. NSCAT twice-daily SIR-enhanced scatterometer EASE-grid 2.0 radar backscatter. doi:<https://doi.org/TBD>.
- Long, D. G.. 2017a. Comparison of SeaWinds backscatter imaging algorithms. *IEEE J. Sel. Topics in Applied Earth Observations* 10(3), 2214–2231. doi:10.1109/JSTARS.2016.2626966.
- Long, D. G.. 2017b. Comparison of SeaWinds Backscatter Imaging Algorithms. *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations* 10(3), 2214–2231. doi:10.1109/JSTARS.2016.2626966.
- Long, D. G.. 2017c. Polar applications of spaceborne scatterometers. *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations* 10(3), 2307–2320. doi:10.1109/JSTARS.2016.2629418.
- Long, D. G. and M. J. Brodzik. 2016b, May. Optimum Image Formation for Spaceborne Microwave Radiometer Products. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* 54(5), 2763–2779. doi:10.1109/TGRS.2015.2505677.

- Long, D. G., M. J. Brodzik, and M. A. Hardman. 2019. Enhanced-Resolution SMAP Brightness Temperature Image Products. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* 57(7), 4151–4163. doi:10.1109/TGRS.2018.2889427.
- Long, D. G. and R. O. W. Franz. 2016b. Band-limited Signal Reconstruction from Irregular Samples with Variable Apertures. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* 54(4), 2424–2436. doi:10.1109/TGRS.2015.2501366.
- Meissner, T., L. Ricciardulli, and F. J. Wentz. 2017. Capability of the SMAP mission to measure ocean surface winds in storms. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society* 98(8), 1660–1677. doi:10.1175/BAMS-D-16-0052.1.
- Naderi, F., M. H. Freilich, and D. G. Long. 1991. Spaceborne radar measurement of wind velocity over the ocean—an overview of the NSCAT scatterometer system. *Proceedings of the IEEE* 79(6), 850–866. doi:10.1109/5.90163.
- Paget, A. P., D. G. Long, and N. M. Madsen. 2016. Rapidsat diurnal cycles over land. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* 54(6), 3336–3344. doi:10.1109/TGRS.2016.2515022.
- Perry, K.. 2001. QuikSCAT Science Data Products User’s Manual, ver. 2.1. Document D-18053, Jet Propulsion Laboratory, Pasadena, CA, 2001.
- Pitas, I. and A. Venetsanopoulos. 1986. Nonlinear mean filters in image processing. *IEEE Transactions on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing* 34(3), 573–584. doi:10.1109/TASSP.1986.1164857.
- Spencer, M. W., W.-Y. Tsai, and D. G. Long. 2003. High resolution measurements with a spaceborne pencil-beam scatterometer using combined range/doppler discrimination techniques. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* 41(3), 567–481. doi:10.1109/TGRS.2003.809938.
- Spencer, M. W., C. Wu, and D. G. Long. 2000. Improved resolution backscatter measurements with the seawinds pencil-beam scatterometer. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* 38(1), 89–104. doi:10.1109/36.823904.
- Stephen, H. and D. G. Long. 2007. Spatial and temporal behavior of microwave backscatter directional modulation over the Saharan ergs. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* 45(5), 1164–1173. doi:10.1109/TGRS.2007.892584.
- Ulaby, F. T. and D. G. Long. 2014. *Microwave Radar and Radiometric Remote Sensing*. Ann Arbor, MI, USA: University of Michigan Press.
- Wikipedia. visited 8 Oct. 2016. Geometric mean. Online, http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Geometric_mean.

Appendices

A QSCAT Projections and Grids

Table 7: QSCAT 25 km product EASE-Grid 2.0 projections and grid dimensions, produced for compatibility with CETB ESDR data products (Brodzik et al., 2021).

Name	Projection	Resolution (km)	Cols	Rows	Latitude Extent	Longitude Extent
EASE2-T25km	Temperate and Tropical Cylindrical	25.0	2600	540	$\pm 67.0576406^\circ$	$\pm 180^\circ$
EASE2-T3.125km	Temperate and Tropical Cylindrical	3.125	15750	4320	$\pm 67.0576406^\circ$	$\pm 180^\circ$
EASE2-N25km	Northern Lambert Azimuthal	25.0	720	720	$0^\circ-90^\circ$	$\pm 180^\circ$
EASE2-N3.125km	Northern Lambert Azimuthal	3.125	5760	5760	$0^\circ-90^\circ$	$\pm 180^\circ$
EASE2-S25km	Southern Lambert Azimuthal	25.0	720	720	$-90^\circ-0^\circ$	$\pm 180^\circ$
EASE2-S3.125km	Southern Lambert Azimuthal	3.125	5760	5760	$-90^\circ-0^\circ$	$\pm 180^\circ$

B QSCAT Data Definition

B.1 File Requirements

Following Brodzik et al. (2021), QSCAT product file requirements include:

- Output file format shall be acceptable for NSIDC DAAC to easily ingest to ECS
- File size maximum will be < 1 GB (larger files are allowed in ECS, but fast network speeds cannot always be assumed)
- Files will conform to netCDF-CF 1.6 conventions for all but the requirement that puts the lat/lon arrays into the file; however, we will include CF-compliant coordinate variables with projected coordinate locations
- Files should pass CF-compliance-checking for all but the lat/lon arrays (we used JPL compliance-checker)
- Each file will contain 1 or more more array variables, with associated ancillary variables, possibly different ancillary variables for each gridding technique. We may have a practical limit on the number of ancillary variables to include, limited by maximum file size
- Each file of the same type (GRD or SIR) will contain the same file-level metadata for that type.
- We will follow the DRY (Don't Repeat Yourself) principle: Metadata will not be duplicated at multiple places in the same file
- DRY exception: Time values will be machine- and human-readable
- DRY exception: Some projection metadata may be in multiple forms (a proj4 string and/or a WKT string)
- Variable/attribute names will be CF-compliant whenever possible

The QSCAT .nc files work with gdal utility, *gdal_translate*, to produce a geoTIFF version of each of the data variables <variable_name> in the file, (details in Brodzik et al. (2018)), for e.g.:

```
$ gdal_translate -of GTiff -b 1 \
NETCDF:''cetb.nc':<variable_name> variable_name.tif
```

B.2 Filename Convention

QSCAT data are distributed by the NSIDC DAAC (<http://nsidc.org/data/nsidc-TBD>).

Filenames are:

```
<product_id>-<grid_name>-<platform_sensor>-<yyyyddd>
-<channel_id>-<pass>-<algorithm>-<input_source>-<version>.nc
```

where parts of the filename are described in Table 8.

Table 8: QSCAT file naming convention

Part	Description	Values
<product_id>	NSIDC unique data product id	NSIDC-TBD
<grid_name>	EASE-Grid 2.0 grid id	See Table 7
<platform>	Satellite platform	QuikSCAT and ADEOS2
<sensor>	Sensor name	SeaWinds
<yyyyddd>	Date	4-digit year and 3-digit day-of-year
<channel_id>	Channel (frequency in GHz and polarization)	14 followed by polarization, one of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HH = horizontal-horizontal • VV = vertical-vertical
<pass>	Pass direction (T grids) or LTOD (N or S grids)	one of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • B = Both (all measurements) • A = Ascending • D = Descending • M = Morning • E = Evening
<algorithm>	Reconstruction algorithm	one of GRD or SIR
<version>	Version number	production version number

B.3 File Content, v1.0

The following is a sample NetCDF `ncdump -h` utility output for a QSCAT v1.0 3.125 km SIR file. File-level metadata and processing details vary depending on projection, spatial resolution and processing details (method, input file list, etc.).

```
netcdf BYU-QSCAT-EASE2_S3.125km-QuikSCAT_Seawinds-1997119_1997126-14VV-M-SIR-v1.0 {
dimensions:
time = UNLIMITED ; // (1 currently)
y = 5760 ;
x = 5760 ;
...
}
```